

The Electrochemical Reduction of Acetylacetone*

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Manuscript received 9 November 1976, revised 29 March 1978, accepted 22 August 1978

Acetylacetone is reduced at different cathodes like zinc, lead, cadmium, copper and platinum. This study was carried out in three media (acidic, neutral and alkaline). The metals with high hydrogen overvoltage like zinc, lead and cadmium are more active in acetylacetone reduction than those with low hydrogen overvoltage like copper and platinum. The reduction efficiency increases with increasing acetylacetone concentration.

CARBONYL compounds can undergo several step-wise reduction reactions resulting in the formation of several products. These include the possible reduction products like hydrocarbon alcohol, bimolecular pinacol and organometallic compounds¹. The possible formation of any of these products depends on the type of electrode and the conditions of electrolysis²⁻⁴.

The mechanism of electrochemical reduction of carbonyl compounds has been subject of study by many authors and several theories were presented to explain the process⁵⁻⁸. According to these theories the reduction of carbonyl compounds involves the formation of a free radical

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals used were reagent grade. The anode was made of platinum with a surface area = 2 cm², while the cathode was made of either zinc, lead, cadmium, copper or platinum with the surface area of 5.0 cm² except that of copper which was 3.2 cm².

Measurements and Calculations :

(a) Current efficiency of reduction (reducibility). The diagram in Fig. 1 illustrates the circuit and apparatus used for these measurements. The reducibility was calculated from the following equation⁹

$$\text{Reducibility} = \frac{V - V'}{V} \times 100$$

Fig. 1. Apparatus for measuring current efficiency.

* This paper is part of the M. Sc. thesis of one of the authors (H. M. Killa).

where V and \hat{V} refer to volume of hydrogen gas collected in the coulometer and over the working cathode respectively.

(b) *Polarization*: These measurements were carried out galvanostatically by applying a constant current for three minutes and then measuring the electrode potential against a saturated calomel electrode. The current applied was increased and the corresponding potential measured, allowing thereby sufficient time for equilibrium attainment after every measurements.

(c) *The order of reaction*: The calculation⁸ of the order of the overall electrode reaction relative to the depolarizer was carried out by plotting $\log C_c$ against $\log i$ at constant polarization potential since:

$$\log i = n \log C + K$$

where n is the order, and C is the concentration of the depolarizer.

Results and Discussion

The results of the current efficiency measurements (reducibility) relating to the different media (either 0.4 M Na₂SO₄, 1 M H₂SO₄, or 0.4 M NaOH) at the different electrodes used are displayed in Fig. 2. It is evident that metals with high hydrogen overvoltage (e.g., zinc, lead and cadmium) are more active in acetylaceton reduction than those with low hydrogen overvoltage (e.g., copper and platinum) which is in accordance with earlier observations⁹. It is also apparent that the reduction efficiency increases with increasing acetylaceton concentration. This could be explained by the increasing adsorption of the molecular acetylaceton on the cathode surface on increasing its concentration¹⁰. Furthermore, the similarity between the reduction efficiency behaviour, shown in Fig. 2, and an adsorption isotherm is compatible with the assumption that the reduction process on the cathode is preceded by an adsorption stage¹¹.

Probable factors that can influence the reduction process under consideration could be (a) the nature of the cathode, (b) the pH value of the aqueous solution of acetylaceton which in turn will decide the equilibrium keto \rightleftharpoons enol of the tautomeric forms of acetylaceton.

In the case of zinc, lead and cadmium electrodes, the lowest reducibility was observed in alkaline medium particularly at low concentration of the depolarizer. This is parallel with regarding the acidic or the neutral solutions to contain higher concentration of the reducible keto form of acetylaceton than in the case of alkaline solution. On the other hand, the observed reducibility on electrodes with low hydrogen overvoltage (copper and platinum) reflects the nature of the electrodes rather than that of keto \rightleftharpoons enol equilibrium of the depolarizer.

Fig. 2 Effect of the electrode material on the current efficiency ACAC.

Increasing the acetylaceton concentration results into a more positive value for the cathodic potential on using all electrodes in alkaline, acidic, and neutral media at low current densities. This situation is reversed in some cases at higher current densities (see Fig. 3 for representative examples).

It is to be noted that the reduction on electrodes with higher hydrogen overvoltage took place at more cathodic potentials. At a specific electrode, e.g., copper and lead, the reduction process occurred at the most negative potential in neutral medium and at the least negative potential in acidic medium. This is an expected observation since at pH value of the range 7-8 the hydrogen overvoltage is maximum and decreases in acidic or alkaline media⁹.

The order of the overall electrode reaction (n), with respect to acetylaceton, was calculated from the effect of concentration on the cathodic potentials of reduction and the results are listed in Tables 1-3. It was found that (n) is characterized by positive values under all conditions especially at low current

Fig. 3. Cathodic polarization for the reduction of acetylacetone on copper in acidic, neutral, and alkaline media (acetylacetone concentrations ; 1=0.01 M, 2=0.10 M, 3=0.50 M) at 30°.

TABLE 1—THE ORDER OF THE OVERALL ELECTRODE REACTION (n) FOR ETHYLACETONE REDUCTION IN NEUTRAL MEDIUM (30°)

Electrode material E(volt)	Zinc	Lead	Cadmium	Copper	Platinum
0.6	—	+0.07	—	+0.14	+0.12
0.7	—	—	—	—	—
0.8	—	+0.05	+0.30	+0.14	+0.18
0.9	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	—	—	+0.22	—	—
1.1	—	—	—	—	+0.38
1.2	—	—	—	+0.54	—
1.3	—	—	—	+0.56	+0.38
1.4	+0.20	—	—	—	—
1.5	+0.245	+0.20	+0.19	—	—
1.6	—	—	+0.18	—	—
1.7	+0.40	+0.32	—	—	—
1.8	+0.44	—	—	—	—

 TABLE 2—THE ORDER OF THE OVERALL ELECTRODE REACTION (n) FOR ACETYLACETONE REDUCTION, IN ACIDIC MEDIUM (30°)

Electrode material E(volt)	Lead	Cadmium	Copper	Platinum
0.1	—	—	—	—
0.15	—	—	—	-1.2
0.2	—	—	+0.1	-0.38
0.3	—	—	+0.02	—
0.4	—	—	—	+1.16
0.5	+0.23	—	-0.4	+1.11
0.6	+0.22	—	-0.52	—
0.7	—	0.49	—	—
0.8	+0.49	0.25	—	—
0.9	—	0.195	—	—
1.0	+0.52	0.197	—	—

densities probably as a result of the depolarization effect of acetylacetone. However, a negative value for (n) was deduced for cases with distinctly low values of reducibility (see Fig. 3 for the copper electrode in acidic medium) whereas at higher current densities acetylacetone ceases to behave as a depolarizer. This behaviour is explained by the inhibition of the hydrogen evolution process by the adsorption of acetylacetone on the cathode.

 TABLE 3—THE ORDER OF THE OVERALL ELECTRODE REACTION (n) FOR ACETYLACETONE REDUCTION, IN ALKALINE MEDIUM (30°)

Electrode material E(volt)	Zinc	Lead	Cadmium	Copper
0.2	—	—	—	—
0.3	—	—	—	—
0.4	—	—	—	—
0.5	—	—	—	—
0.6	—	—	—	+0.13
0.7	—	—	—	—
0.8	—	+0.29	—	+0.14
0.9	—	—	—	—
0.95	—	—	+0.45	—
1.0	—	+0.22	+0.34	—
1.1	—	—	—	—
1.2	—	—	—	—
1.3	—	—	—	+0.38
1.4	+1.13	-0.20	—	+0.27
1.5	+0.66	—	—	—
1.6	—	-0.31	-0.09	—
1.7	—	—	-0.14	—
1.8	+1.1	—	—	—
1.9	—	—	—	—
2.0	+0.64	—	—	—

References

1. A. P. TOMILOV, S. G. MAIRANOUSKY, M. YA. FIOSSHIN and V. A. SMIRNOV, "Elektrokhimiya Organicheskikh Soedinenii", Leningrad, 1968, p. 211.
2. S. OHKI and N. NOIKE, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1952, **72**, 490.
3. A. P. TOMILOV and B. L. KLUEV, *Elektrokhimiya*, 1966, **2**, 1405.
4. V. O. REISCHFIELD and S. K. KAUDRNA, *Troudi L. T. Inst.*, 1956, p. 100.
5. P. I. ELVING and I. T. LEONE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 1021.
6. L. I. ANTROPOV, *USBEKHY KHIMIYA*, 1956, **25**, 1043.
7. F. EL-CHEIKH, Z. H. KHALIL and AHMED I. KHODAIR, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, **32b**, 581.
8. S. V. GARBACHEV, *Troudi M.X.T. Inst., Moscow*, 1973, **76**, p. 85.
9. L. I. ANTROPOV, "Theoretical Electrochemistry", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1972, p. 456.
10. T. SEKINE, A. YAMURA and K. SUGINO, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1965, **122**, 439.
11. I. I. ANTROPOV, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1950, **24**, 1428.